

Pass code sentence

*Vereist

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1. Enter the pass code sentence to access the computer (ALL CAPS) *

Data Management Plan

Please read this Data Management Plan before submitting
Lead researcher: Professor Hutseephuts
ORCID: 0000-7f80-9074-7564
Others with data management responsibilities: PhD candidate (name to be confirmed).

This is the first version of the data management plan of the research project about ghost sightings around Halloween. A Data Management Plan (DMP) is a living document, and will be updated as the project progresses

Title of research project

The Horror of All Hallows' Eve: A socio-cultural-biological frame on ghost sightings in several places in Europe as influenced by various natural factors, including, but not limited to floods, famines and fauna, as well as local imaginations, informed by ethnography.

Please specify the origin of the data: will new data be collected or produced and/or will existing data be re-used?

I will collect new data by holding interviews (with an audio recorder), making photographs (with a photo camera) and observations (sketches and notes on paper). I may ask a PhD researcher to check if we could benefit from re-using an existing dataset on bat infections around the world. They may be an important biological factor.

Is it necessary to transfer the (physical or digital) data assets to other locations or research partners? If yes, please describe how you will secure the file transfer.

Yes, I will have to transfer the data from the audio device and photo camera to my laptop, and I will have to transport all my equipment across several national borders. I will get advice from the university legal department to help me with the legal proceedings for such border crossings and complying with GDPR outside of the EU, and IT will help me with encryption and will show me how to erase the materials on the audio recorder once they have been transferred onto the laptop. I will also share my data with collaborators in Mexico so I will make use of secure file-sharing services provided by the university.

In which digital repository (or data archive) will you archive your data?

The anonymised part of the dataset will be uploaded to Dataverse; any personal data that need to be retained will be archived in the secure offline archive of the university. The research software/code created in this project will be deposited at GitHub.

Will your dataset be allocated a persistent identifier (e.g. a DOI-code)?

Dataverse will auto-generate a DOI and there will be a code for the materials stored in the offline archive. I myself have an ORCID, of course.

Please indicate the licence and/or terms of use under which you share your data.

The publicly shared data will receive a CC BY 4.0 licence, meaning that anyone can use the data as long as they acknowledge me as a creator.

Will you follow a specific metadata standard?

I will use the Dublin Core Metadata Standard, which provides fifteen core fields about the data. I will use the Dublin Core Metadata Standard, which provides fifteen core fields about the data. I will also investigate the metadata standards being used by the researchers on bat infections to ensure we can make the datasets interoperable with each other.

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